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Monitoring Infection Prevention and Control Practices in Orthopedic Surgeries: A Cross-Sectional Study at Lady Reading Hospital, PeshawarShabir Ahmed¹, Atta U Rehman², Nafees U Rehman³, Shabir Khattak⁴, Zainab Liaqat*⁵

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Orthopedic Surgery, Surgical Site Infection (SSI), Infection Prevention And Control, MRSA, Hand Hygiene.

Shabir Ahmed

Sarhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Sarhad university of Science and Information Technology.

Atta U Rehman

Sarhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Sarhad university of Science and Information Technology.

Nafees U Rehman

Sarhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Sarhad university of Science and Information Technology.

Shabir Khattak

Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar

Zainab Liaqat (Corresponding Author)

Sarhad Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Sarhad university of Science and Information Technology.
Email: Zainab.siahs@suit.edu.pk

Orthopedic surgeries, particularly those involving implants, are associated with a significant risk of surgical site infections (SSIs). These infections increase morbidity, mortality, hospital stay, and healthcare costs. Effective infection prevention and control (IPC) practices are essential to mitigate these risks. To evaluate current IPC practices in the orthopedic operation theater at Lady Reading Hospital, identify gaps, and propose evidence-based recommendations to reduce SSIs. A quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 110 healthcare professionals working in the orthopedic operation theater at LRH. Data were collected using structured questionnaires assessing adherence to IPC protocols, including hand hygiene, sterilization, PPE usage, environmental control, and operating room practices. Data were analyzed using SPSS. Compliance with hand hygiene (90%) and availability of handwashing facilities (96%) were high. Awareness regarding instrument sterilization was reported by 97.7% of participants. Proper draping and aseptic practices were observed in 96–97% of respondents. However, only 58% reported limiting operating room traffic, and 41% confirmed using a new instrument set for wound closure. Infection control training effectiveness received moderate support (62%). While fundamental IPC practices demonstrate strong compliance, significant gaps remain in operating room traffic control, wound closure instrument practices, and structured training programs. Strengthening surveillance, education, and policy enforcement is essential to reduce SSI risk in orthopedic surgeries.

INTRODUCTION:

Orthopedic surgery focuses on diagnosing, treating, rehabilitating, and preventing disorders of the musculoskeletal system, including bones, joints, ligaments, tendons, muscles, and nerves. Common procedures include arthroscopy, arthroplasty (joint replacement), fracture fixation, bone grafting, osteotomy, and spinal fusion [1].

Procedures such as total knee replacement and hip arthroplasty frequently involve the implantation of prostheses, plates, screws, and rods. While these interventions restore mobility and quality of life, they also increase susceptibility to infection due to the presence of foreign materials that facilitate bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation [2].

Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) remain one of the most serious postoperative complications. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, SSIs account for approximately 22% of healthcare-associated infections. The National Healthcare Safety Network defines SSI as an infection occurring at or near the surgical incision within 30 days of surgery or up to one year when implants are involved [3].

The most common causative organism in orthopedic SSIs is *Staphylococcus aureus*, including Methicillin-resistant strains (MRSA). Studies report MRSA prevalence in Pakistan ranging from 38–50%, significantly higher than in many high-income countries [4].

It is a great challenge for the health care provider to prevent infections in orthopedic procedures due to use of heavy equipment's and bulky instruments along with the external plates, screws, nails and rods. Although the preoperative use of antibiotics has been widely discussed and is routinely used as an important strategy for infection control, the way these protocols are monitored and enforced in clinical practice remains a significant difference [5]. Surgical site infections (SSI) in orthopedic surgeries are caused by a combination of factors related to the patient, the surgery, and the preoperative period. These factors include: Increased age (especially over 60 years), obesity (BMI >25), diabetes mellitus (strong independent risk factor), smoking, comorbidities like hypertension and congestive heart failure, general poor clinical condition or infirmity, longer surgery duration, multiple fractures (>2), surgical site (trauma-related sites have higher SSI risk compared to spine or arthrosis), number of surgeries (repeated surgeries increase risk). The personnel's are trained to follow hand hygiene and place the waste materials into the color coded containers that placed near to OT [6].

Infection can be controlled by using principles as given below

Hand hygiene: Using proper and regular hand washing help to reduce the spread of infections

Personnel protective equipment's (PPE): It is necessary to use the PPE such as Gloves, mask, Eye goggles etc. to reduce the exposure to Infective agents.

Respiratory Hygiene: Cover Mouth and Nose especially when Coughing, talking, sneezing and speaking.

Disinfection and Sterilization: The surfaces and the equipment's are cleaned on the regular bases to reduce the contamination.

Waste management: the waste management is safely controlled by disposing the wastes into the different color coded dustbins indicated by their colors.

Education and Training: Educate the healthcare workers by seminars to control the infection from spreading [7].

Aims:

This study aimed to evaluate and improve infection-control practices during orthopaedic surgeries at Lady

Reading Hospital.

Objectives:

To access the current infection control protocols being followed in the operating theatre of orthopaedic surgery at LRH, Peshawar.

To observe Hand hygiene practices and use of personal protective equipment by the surgical team.

To evaluate sterilization and disinfectant methods for surgical instruments and rooms.

To enhance the awareness and training of healthcare staff regarding infection prevention and control standards

Literature Review

Orthopaedic implant surgeries, particularly in the lower limbs, are uniquely predisposed to infections due to the presence of foreign materials like plates, screws, and rods [8]. As mentioned in 2022 by the Chau R that these materials provide an ideal surface for bacterial adherence and biofilm formation. Biofilms significantly complicate treatment as they shield bacteria from antibiotics and the host's immune defenses, often requiring surgical intervention to manage infections [9]. According to Zhu Y, lower limb surgeries such as fracture fixation, joint replacement, and deformity correction are not only essential for restoring mobility but are also prone to higher risks of SSIs [10]. Bader T observed that "Surgical Site Infection (SSI) for orthopedic surgery is a clinical problem that occurs in orthopedic wards for patients undergoing orthopedic surgery" [11]. It has been stated that the incidence of SSIs in orthopedic implant surgeries varies globally, with rates ranging between 0.5% and 5% in high-income countries [12]. However, these numbers are often significantly higher in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) due to resource constraints, lack of standardized aseptic protocols, and limited access to advanced surgical facilities [13]. Surgical diseases in Pakistan are very heavy, with high incidences of trauma, degenerative bone diseases, and emergency abdominal surgeries requiring immediate as well as effective interventions. Total knee replacement, hip arthroplasty, and fracture management are orthopedic surgeries that require precision and advanced intraoperative techniques to achieve functional recovery and reduce long-term morbidity. Frassanito L believed that it is one of the major challenge in optimizing surgical techniques in Pakistan that exists because of the minimal implementation of minimally invasive methods such as laparoscopic and arthroscopic surgeries. Open surgical procedures remain widespread, yet they cause additional infection hazards, produce greater postoperative discomfort, and need prolonged recovery times. Pakistan lacks sufficient funds, proper training, and appropriate healthcare policies needed for large-scale implementation of such practices in surgical education and practice [14].

Methodology

Study Design Quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Setting Orthopedic Operation Theater, Lady Reading Hospital (LRH), Peshawar.

Study Population Healthcare personnel involved in orthopedic surgeries.

Sample Size participants including:

Surgeons

Trainee Medical Officers (TMO)

House Officers (HO)

Scrub and Circulating Nurses

Surgical Technicians

Anesthesia staff

Radiology personnel

Inclusion Criteria OT personnel with 1 month to 10 years of experience.

Exclusion Criteria Non-orthopedic surgeries and minor procedures not requiring sterile OT

Results

110 samples were collected from the personnel's working in the orthopedic operation theater for this comprehensive research that examines the infection prevention control practices in orthopedic surgeries. This research focus mainly on the factors that adherence to the hand hygiene standards as defined by (WHO), availability of hand washing facility close to operation theater and biomedical waste container (color coded), sterilization and cleaning protocols for the instruments, surgical attire such as Gown or environmental control measures in operation theater. This study investigates from the personnel's that overall 90% employees follow the hand hygiene practices defined by the world health organization and 96% report access to hand washing facilities close to operating rooms . 93.7% respondents report that they are fully aware about instrument sterilization practices. 96.5 employees agree that draping and prepping system is properly and in correct way used. 82.8% personnel's were in favor of well-maintained and managed ventilation system (Laminar airflow) in Operating rooms also 97.5% of surgical team practices and aseptic practice like gowning, dressing and draping which contribute to the strong field of sterility.

However gaps remain only 58% of survey indicates that surgeons limit the number of personnel's in the operating rooms during surgery which can lead to an increase risk of contamination from the overcrowded conditions. Just 41% confirms that new set of instrument are used at the end of the survey for the wound closure and suggests that these devices may be the vector for postoperative infections in orthopedic surgeries. The survey on the efficacy of infection control training yielded mixed results with 62% indicating support for the systemic assessment emphasizing the importance of ongoing and enhanced educations. This research highlights the strong framework for the infection prevention control in orthopedic surgeries while finding the areas that need to be improved for making ensures for the better patients outcomes through measures such as controlling personnel's presence in the operating rooms more than required for a surgical procedures. Ensuring that only new set of sterile instruments are used for the wound closures at the end of the surgeries and training programs for infection prevention control to reduce the surgical site infections.

The concepts of these ideas can improve the safety measures in hospitals and decrease the rate of morbidity, mortality and prolonged hospital stays associated with surgical site infections.

Discussion

This research identified that adherence to the infection prevention control practices in orthopedic surgeries was consistence with the highest compliance hand hygiene standards, availability of waste containers (color coded) ,disinfection and sterilization of instruments in the correct ways [15] .

This study of research found out that mostly personnel's follow the proper hand hygiene and all the protocols that can help to prevent the infections and further educate the team to follow all the needed and necessary standards to promote the patients outcomes.

The low standardization in the surgical hand hygiene may reflect the gaps in the staff training lack of monitoring .These findings of the study urge that more stress need to be used for hand hygiene in the orthopedic OT .

These results are consistent with those reported by Ahmad et al (2021), who found suboptimal compliance with hand hygiene in surgical wards, however unlike their study, this research findings show improved performance in the use of PPE (Personal protective equipment's) [15].

In this research study, 90% of personnel reported following WHO-recommended hand hygiene practices, and 96% had access to hand-washing facilities near the operating theatre. These findings are higher than the

compliance rates reported in many hospitals worldwide (often 40–60%) but align with those seen after the implementation of WHO's multimodal hand hygiene improvement strategies [16].

Almost 98.8% Staff personnels reported that laminar airflow and ventilation systems were well-maintained but the recent systemic review in orthopedic procedures found no consistent reduction in surgical site infections attributed to laminar airflow alone [17-19].

According to this study research 97.7% staff are aware of proper instruments sterilization and 96-97% reported the right way of draping, prepping and gowning and these rates are parallel published surveys showing high reported knowledge yet and also highlights the caveat that knowledge does not mean always to equate with the correct practices on the direct audit [20-21]

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

This research study based on findings of infection prevention control practices in orthopedic operation theater. Using 110 samples among the medical professional who were working in orthopedic surgeries. The researchers found that whether the medical professional are following the important protocols such as hand hygiene (WHO) practices as reported 90% follow, 96% reported the availability of hand washing facility near the operation theater . 97.7% employs confirmed that they are fully aware about the surgical instruments sterilization and cleaning protocols.

The deficiency of regularity in hand hand hygiene was one of the most critical aspect also WHO recommends hand washing as the 'essential' approach to infection prevention but in this research study many staff members were aware and showed more adherence. Comparing this study findings with National and International studies levels made it clear that infection prevention control is not limited to the particular hospital (LRH). Studies conducted in various regions showed sub standards practices for the infection prevention control.

While the samples of this study provides the valuable comprehension into the correct practices and demonstrates the area that needs the attention. This study emphasizes the requirements for training, seminars, professional development and frequent review of infection prevention control practices. According to this research study some gaps are still significant in the term of international standards in spite of some practices which are being established .Combination of education. Monitoring & administrative support not only decrease the risk of infection at (SSIs) but also improve patient outcomes in orthopedic surgeries.

REFERENCES

- Surgical site infection event (SSI). NationalHealthcare Safety Network. Accessed April 26, 2022.
- Liang, Z., Rong, K., Gu, W., Yu, X., Fang, R., Deng, Y., & Lu, L. (2019). Surgical site infection following elective orthopaedic surgeries in geriatric patients: Incidence and associated risk factors. *International Wound Journal*, 16(3), 773–780.
- Le, J., Dong, Z., Liang, J., Zhang, K., Li, Y., Cheng, M., & Zhao, Z. (2020). Surgical site infection following traumatic orthopaedic surgeries in geriatric patients: Incidence and prognostic risk factors. *International Wound Journal*, 17(1), 206–213.
- Liu H, Wang Y, Xing H, Chang Z, Pan J. Risk factors for deep surgical site infections following orthopedic trauma surgery: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Journal of orthopaedic surgery and research*. 2024;19(1):811.
- Regmi A, Ojha N, Singh M, Ghimire A, Kharel N. Risk factors associated with surgical site infection following cesarean section in tertiary care hospital, Nepal. *International Journal of Reproductive Medicine*. 2022;2022(1):4442453.

- Bucataru A, Balasoiu M, Ghenea AE, Zlatian OM, Vulcanescu DD, Horhat FG, et al. Factors Contributing to Surgical Site Infections: A Comprehensive Systematic Review of Etiology and Risk Factors. *Clinics and Practice*. 2023;14(1):52-68.
- Raza, M., Hafeez, M. A., Abbas, S., Hameed, M. U., & Awais, M. (2025). Risk factors of surgical site infection in orthopedic implants following lower limb surgery. *Kashf Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1).
- Meng, M., Zhou, J., Zhang, Y., & Li, X. (2023). Infection risks of orthopedic implants and their clinical management. *Injury*, 54(3), 684–692.
- Al Muderis M. *Osseointegration for Amputees: Past, Present and Future: Basic Science, Innovations in Surgical Technique, Implant Design and Rehabilitation Strategies*. 2021.
- Chua R, Lim SK, Chee CF, Chin SP, Kiew LV, Sim KS, et al. Surgical site infection and development of antimicrobial sutures: a review. *European Review for Medical & Pharmacological Sciences*. 2022;26(3).
- Li P, Yin R, Cheng J, Lin J. Bacterial biofilm formation on biomaterials and approaches to its treatment and prevention. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2023;24(14):11680.
- Zhu Y, Yang B, Wang Y. Effects of comfort nursing combined with rehabilitation training on joint function, pain level and quality of life in patients with lower extremity fractures. *Archives of Clinical Psychiatry*. 2023;50(6).
- Cuncannon A, Dosani A, Fast O. Sterile processing in low-and middle-income countries: an integrative review. *Journal of Infection Prevention*. 2021;22(1):28-38.
- Frassanito L, Vergari A, Nestorini R, Cerulli G, Placella G, Pace V, et al. Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) in hip and knee replacement surgery: description of a multidisciplinary program to improve management of the patients undergoing major orthopedic surgery. *Musculoskeletal surgery*. 2020;104:87-92.
- Kadri A, Binkley N, Hare KJ, Anderson PA. Bone health optimization in orthopaedic surgery. *JBJS*. 2020;102(7):574-81.
- Hidron AI, Edwards JE, Patel J, Horan TC, Sievert DM, Pollock DA, Fridkin SK; National Healthcare Safety Network Team; Participating National Healthcare Safety Network Facilities. NHSN annual update: Antimicrobial-resistant pathogens associated with healthcare-associated infections: annual summary of data reported to the National Healthcare Safety Network at the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2006–2007. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol*. 2008;29:996-1011
- World Health Organization. (2016). *Global guidelines for the prevention of surgical site infection*. WHO Press.
- Zhou Y, Li Z and Huang S. Retrospective investigation and analysis of risk factors of incision infection in orthopaedic surgery. *Chinese Journal of Hospital Infectiology* 2013; 23: 3158–3160.
- Rajput, I., Zainab, G., Siddiqi, A. A., Kumar, J., Ahmed, M. W., & Khani, G. M. K. (2022). Incidence of Early Surgical Site Infection (SSI) in Elective Orthopaedic Implant Surgeries. *Journal of Pakistan Orthopaedic Association*.
- Bilal, M., Karamat, A., Basit, M. S., Bashir, M. S., Naqvi, Q., & Hashmi, G. M. (2022). Incidence of Surgical Site Infection in Patients Presented for Orthopaedic Surgery. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*, 16(08), 289.
- Dina, T. K., Aziz, S., Katto, A. A., Idrees, Z., & Noor, S. S. (2023). Assessment of Incidence of Superbugs and Antibiotic Resistance in Orthopaedics: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Pakistan Orthopaedic Association*.